

The Impact of Corporate Governance on Adjusting Profit of Vietnamese Agricultural Enterprises

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Abstract:

The study was conducted to examine the impact of corporate governance on the earnings management of Vietnamese agricultural enterprises. Through Stat software to perform quantitative research method by descriptive statistics, analyzing correlation relationships among factors, running regression of Pooled OLS, FEM, REM, GLS, System GMM, testing diseases of the model and the validity of the model. The research results will enrich a series of historical studies on the impact of corporate governance on corporate earnings.

Keywords: corporate governance, earnings management, Vietnamese agricultural enterprises.

1. Introduction

The late 1990s and early 21st century saw a series of financial scandals by companies across the US and Europe: Enron, HealthSouth, Parmalat, Tyco, WorldCom and Xerox. The core of these scandals is mainly due to the phenomenon of corporate earnings management (Goncharov, 2005). Profit adjustment has become a major and consistent concern among scientists and managers, as demonstrated in many previous studies (Watts and Zimmerman, 1990; Gaver et al., 1995; Healy and Wahlen, 1999; Fields et al., 2001). According to Loomis (1999), earnings management conceals the actual performance and financial potential of businesses and obscures the truths that stakeholders should know.

As the researches mentioned earlier, the practice of adjusting profits creates information about accounting profits that is not reliable enough, does not accurately reflect the performance of a company. For example, in Vietnam, many enterprises have the difference in financial statements before and after the audit, specifically: The Vietnam Economic Times has reflected the difference in profit after tax of Vietnam Gas Corporation. Male (GAS), whereby the company's 2018 profit after tax before and after the audit is up to 646 billion dong (Bach Hue, 2019); Another case is Hoang Anh Gia Lai Joint Stock Company (HAG) whose profit changed from a profit of VND253 billion to a loss of VND2,025 billion after the audit (Linh Dan, 2020). This leads to concerns about the accuracy of financial statements and transparency in information disclosure.

Bookkeeping returns will become more reliable and of higher quality when managers reduce opportunity behavior due to the use of tight surveillance systems (Wild, 1996; Dechow et al., 1996). Xie et al (2001) and Klein (2002b) show that corporate governance reduces a manager's ability to adjust earnings, thereby assisting investors by aligning management goals with shareholders' policy, thereby enhancing the reliability of financial information and the integrity of the financial reporting process (Watts and Zimmerman, 1986). Liu and Lu (2007) argue that corporate governance is significantly related to earnings management and that problems that exist in the enterprise can also be overcome by good corporate governance practices. Therefore, corporate governance mechanism will limit the ability to regulate internal profits and protect outside interests.

Vietnamese agricultural enterprises face many difficulties in corporate governance and earnings management to mobilize capital.

2. Literature review

According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (1999, 2004), "Corporate governance is a system built to control and control enterprises. Corporate governance structure shows how to distribute rights and responsibilities among the various components related to a joint stock company such as: Board of Directors, directors, shareholders, and other entities. relate to. Corporate governance also clearly

explains rules and procedures for making decisions related to running the company. In this way, corporate governance also provides a structure through which people set company goals, and also the means to achieve goals or monitor performance. "

John and Senbet (1998) provide a more comprehensive definition where corporate governance is a mechanism by which corporate stakeholders exercise control over those in the company and management to ensure that protect their interests.

Corporate governance as defined by Mathiesen, H., (2002) is a business field that studies how to promote effective business governance in joint stock companies by using structures. Interest incentives, organizational structures and rules - rules. CG is often limited to questions about improving financial performance, for example, what ways business owners encourage their managers to use them to deliver return on investment. higher.

A study by Metrick and Ishii (2002) defines corporate governance from the investor's point of view when it comes to corporate governance that is committed to paying a worthy return on invested capital and ensuring efficient operations. business activities of enterprises from investment capital. Consequently, corporate governance affects a firm's ability to access capital markets.

Messier et al. (2008) redefined corporate governance as a system of people, processes and operations that can help secure and manage assets. Many researchers consider this an important tool for monitoring management activities (Chung et al., 2002; Davidson et al., 2005; Skousen et al. 2005; Chen et al., 2006; Lin and Hwang , 2010).

Thus, it can be seen that there is no single definition of corporate governance that applies to all situations and institutions. Different definitions of corporate governance derive from the different institutions, legal mechanisms, and business environments in each country. However, most definitions place the enterprise at the center, which can be summarized: Corporate governance is a system of relationships between stakeholders with different interests. , sometimes, conflicting interests involve directing and controlling corporate operations to appropriately divide rights and responsibilities and thereby increase the interests of shareholders (IFC and SSC, 2010).

In recent times, earnings management has been more interested by managers and stakeholders, so researchers have focused on exploiting this issue. However, previous studies have given different definitions of earnings management. Healy and Wahlen (1999) provide a comprehensive definition that earnings manipulation occurs when managers try to alter financial statements that lead to misunderstandings about corporate performance or influence results. results of negotiated contracts based on financial statements (Healy and Wahlen, 1999; Roychowdhury, 2006; Gajevszky, 2014). Ronen and Yaari (2008) define earnings management as a set of management decisions that lead to maximization of value for managers and that earnings reporting is not accurately reflected.

Fischer and Rosensweig (1995) also define profit adjustment as the actions of managers to increase (decrease) reported profits, which defines two important components of earnings management. : consequences and intentions. Asymmetric information allows managers to adjust profits to maximize their personal interests, thereby affecting the quality of financial statements (Gul et al., 2003; Chung et al., 2004; Liu and O'Farrell, 2011). Because information asymmetry exists between people inside the business and people outside the organization, individuals within the organization can rely on their control of financial reporting and access to financial information. key in companies to exaggerate profits or conceal adverse results. From this point of view, management can use different methods such as hiding changes in business performance thereby reducing profit margins (Leuz et al., 2003; Hijazi & Al-Thuneibat , 2015). Profit adjustment is used to reduce costs in managing bonuses, conveniently adjusting liabilities, and additional bonus or fund schemes. Another common definition given by Schipper (1989) is that earnings management deliberately interferes with the financial

reporting process in order to obtain personal benefits for shareholders or managers. Fields et al. (2001) observed that earnings management occurs when managers are not restricted from a firm's right to perform accounting activities. Managers can manipulate accounting statements by adjusting accruals. However, Kaplan's (1985) study shows that the accruals that arise in normal activity are difficult to reflect the manager's opportunistic behavior. Adjusting margins to increase value maximization was first introduced by Holthausen and Leftwich (1983). Here, managerial decision-making power is a vehicle for managers to disclose to investors their personal expectations about the cash flow from a company's future business. Adjusting returns means managers seek to deceive investors by pursuing managerial benefits. Studies of this type of profit adjustment come mainly from Healy, who found that managers use payables to manipulate managerial bonuses. The interests of affected shareholders when adjusting profits bring extraordinary personal benefits to managers.

Earning adjustments are an important area of research, as earnings adjustments can reduce the credibility of financial statements that provide useful information to stakeholders in well-performing capital markets. . As mentioned above, earnings management can be viewed as opportunistic behavior. However, companies may also not publicly adjust profits to reduce the effect of internal disclosure (Lambert, 1984; Suh, 1990; Stocken and Verrecchia, 2004). These studies provide evidence that earnings management can be used as a signaling mechanism to improve blocked communication channels between people within the firm and outside the firm.

Profit adjustment is intended to obtain certain benefits for the business or for managers, or to secure contracts for which binding terms are based on accounting information. Accordingly, there are five main drivers of earnings management that have been mentioned in previous studies: managerial bonuses, debt covenants, capital markets, legal and engine meets the expectations of investors.

Management bonus engine

One of the prominent drivers of the adjustment of returns is the bonuses in the scheme (Healy, 1985; McNichols and Wilson, 1988; Holthausen, Larcker and Sloan, 1995; Gaver, and Austin, 1995; Bergstresser and Philippon, 2006; Houmes and Skantz, 2010). Healy (1985) provided the first evidence of firms' motivations to adjust profits. Accordingly, managers get information from within and have the opportunity to adjust net profits to maximize their benefits. Therefore, it is more likely that managers will seek to increase their profits in the present period (Healy, 1985). In Healy's studies, most bonus regimes had a minimum, but not a limit. Benefit from bonuses that make managers participate in adjusting profits; however, this has not been consistent across countries (Brown and Higgins, 2001). Recent studies have shown that manager's bonuses are related to firm performance and positively correlated with earnings management (Cornett, McNutt and Tehranian, 2009; Giang, Petroni and Wang, 2010). More importantly, managers are able to adjust current profits more relative to future profits to ensure job security (DeFond and Park, 1997). However, a number of previous studies provide evidence that managerial change is also a factor in earnings management. New managers are more likely to engage in earnings management to make a breakout that increases their chances of earning bonuses in the next phase.

Managers tend to act to maximize their benefits. This is the self-interested behavior mentioned in the agency theory. When the management bonus contract is based on the business performance of the business, such as profit or revenue, the managers have an incentive to practice self-interest. Watts & Zimmerman (1990) argues that managers have an incentive to promote future earnings reporting to the current accounting period when an award scheme exists based on profits. Healy (1985) also concluded that managers use accounting judgments to increase profits in order to achieve profit-based bonuses. Recent research by Noronha et al. (2008) shows that the management bonus incentive is the most powerful motive for managers to make profit adjustments in Chinese public companies.

Debt covenant motivation

Another motive for businesses to make earnings adjustments are debt covenants. Typically, long-term debt contracts often include covenants to protect creditors. If the business breaches its debt covenants, it will incur higher costs to pay. Consequently, managers are more likely to adjust earnings to avoid liabilities (DeFond and Jiambalvo, 1994; DeAngelo and Skinner, 1996). Furthermore, firms are also able to avoid reporting losses by adjusting their profits more (Hayn, 1995; Burgstahler and Dichev, 1997b). More importantly, Healy and Wahlen (1999) argue that it takes different managers, opposing or different motives to determine the level of each. Managers, for example, may be motivated to increase profits or to meet analyst forecasts because of the contract of bonuses mentioned above. Gompers et al. (2003) combined 24 different clauses to build a governance index from 1,500 firms. The researchers also noted similar results with Healy's findings. The difference is that McNichols and Wilson use NPLs as a measure of earnings.

Banks and creditors often require businesses to achieve a certain business result expressed through accounting data. If the enterprise fails to comply with the debt agreement, it will be subject to strong pressure from banks and creditors through the cessation of funding or fines for breaching the signed debt agreement. Defond and Jiambalvo (1994) examined a sample of 90 debt covenant violators and found that manipulation firms increased profits a year prior to the year of breach. Sweeney (1994) uses a sample of 130 firms violating the debt covenant and provides evidence that in the years prior to the breach, firms were faced with the high costs of manipulating them by changing Their default accounting processes to increase profits. Referring to the debt covenant refers to agencies and organizations with idle money such as banks, credit institutions and creditors of the business.

Creditors often ask businesses to achieve a certain business result, as shown through accounting data. If the business fails to perform as stated in the debt covenant, it will face strong pressure from creditors through cessation of funding or penalties for breach of the signed debt agreement. Defond and Jiambalvo (1994) study of debt covenant-violating firms and found that firms using debt covenant engines would increase profits one year prior to the current year of violation. This study uses 90 corporate debt covenant samples. Sweeney (1994) also studied companies that violated debt covenants and found that companies in the years prior to their debit breaches faced very high incurable costs, This is also the reason why these companies immediately change their current accounting policies, accounting processes to increase profits.

□ Capital market engines

According to research by Gulzar & Wang (2011), ordinary capital markets include equity markets, business acquisitions, and mergers. When under pressure from the capital market to achieve profit targets such as issuing shares to the public, buying and selling businesses, or merging businesses, profit adjustment occurs. Enterprises make efforts to minimize fluctuations in profit targets between accounting periods in order to keep stock prices stable or increase market prices of stocks. Because, high fluctuation between accounting periods means high risks when investing in that company. As a result, the share price will drop relative to the share price of companies with stable profits over accounting periods. Consequently, managers of listed companies tend to adjust profits (towards leveling) in order to achieve stable profitability between accounting periods to ensure long-term sustainable profits. . Burgstahler & Dichev (1997) shows that managers adjust profits to increase profits or reduce profits. Research by Erickson and Wang (1999) shows that firms inflate profits in order to increase stock prices before mergers.

When there are capital market pressures such as to achieve target returns in order to issue shares to the public or mergers and acquisitions operations, earnings adjustment may occur. Burgstahler & Dichev (1997) provide evidence that managers adjust earnings to report an increase or avoidance of a loss. There have been many studies providing evidence that companies make adjustments to earnings before issuing shares to the public. In Vietnam, Pham Thi Bich Van (2012) provides evidence that the majority of joint stock companies listed on the Vietnamese stock market adjusted to increase profits before issuing shares to the public for the first time (IPO).

There is also evidence that firms inflate profits in order to increase stock prices ahead of mergers (Erickson & Wang, 1999).

Legal motives

Studies show that legal regulations are also the driving force behind profit adjustment. As a rule, enterprises supplying equipment and devices must meet certain profitability targets (Nguyen Tri Tri, 2012). With such strict regulations, businesses in this industry may be able to adjust their profits to meet regulations when they are in trouble. Or regulations on corporate income tax rates can also be the engine of earnings management. Baralexis (2004) found that small firms are actually more concerned with tax cost savings when adjusting profits. As research by Noronha et al. (2008) shows that private companies in China adjust profits because they want to reduce the cost of corporate income tax. Similarly, Nguyen Thi Minh Trang (2012) also showed that unlisted firms in Vietnam tended to reduce profits to save corporate income tax costs.

The motivation to meet investors' expectation

Earnings forecasting companies are more likely to adjust earnings to meet investor expectations (Burgstahler and Eames, 1998; Kasznik, 1999; DeGeorge, Patel and Zeckhauser, 1999; Matsunaga and Park, 2001 ; Bartov, Givoly and Hayn, 2002; Barton and Mercer, 2005; Das, Shroff and Zhang, 2007; Chin, Chen and Hsieh, 2009). Some studies show that regulators appear to adjust profits to prevent profits from falling below the level that analysts forecast (Burgstahler and Eames, 1998; Kasznik, 1999; Matsumoto, 2002; Burgstahler and Eames, 2006). Research by DeAngelo et al. (1996) shows that firms that fail to meet profit growth forecasts, more significantly than firms losing money or inconsistent profit growth are more encouraged to profit adjustment, as they can get more benefits from management (prospect theory) and can also reduce transaction costs with related parties, as terms of the transaction tend to be favorable. more profit for companies with higher profits. Therefore, managers have a strong incentive to adjust profits in order to meet investors' expectations. McVay, Nagar and Tang (2006) find that managers are more likely to adjust earnings in response to analysts' forecasts before selling their shares.

Firms are also more likely to adjust profits to enhance pre-listing corporate value (Hughes, 1986, Clarkson et al., 1992; Teoh, Welch, and Wong, 1998a, b). Cormier and Martinez (2006) provide evidence that firms in France with weak CG are expected to have more earnings corrections after their public offering. Furthermore, when some firms acquire other firms, in which the stock is considered part of the purchase price, the profit is more likely to be increased by the manager by increasing the share price and reduce acquisition costs (Louis, 2004). Furthermore, earnings adjustments may occur due to loan loss (Beaver and Engel, 1996; Beaver, McNichol and Nelson, 2003). In addition, a number of studies have shown that some firms use hedging activities (Barton, 2001) or alter research and development costs to adjust profits (Bushee, 1998). .

3. Research method

3.1. Research data collection

Data used in the study are secondary data, provided from Vietnamese agricultural enterprises, including: Financial statements and other corporate reports The sampled companies are rich companies. Sufficient data in the research period and unchanged accounting period in the research period. Companies for the purposes of research, must be active and their shares are traded regularly.

3.2. Data processing method

First, the thesis identifies research problems, sums up through the studies related to the impact of corporate governance on earnings management, then draws research gaps. Based on an overview of research projects and theoretical bases on the impact of corporate governance on earnings management, research hypotheses related to the impact of corporate governance on earnings management are proposed. export. Next, the graduate student

collects and processes data through Stata 12 software to perform quantitative research methods by descriptive statistics, analyzing correlation relationships between factors, running Pooled regression. OLS, FEM, REM, GLS, System GMM, test the model's diseases (multicollinearity, variance change, autocorrelation), model validity ... to find the most suitable model. . The results collected will be discussed, and then recommendations and conclusions will be made.

3.3. Profit adjustment methods

Profit is the difference between revenue and expenses, from which the recognition of revenue and expense is decisive to the reported profit in a given period. Therefore, the methods that can be used by managers to adjust profits in the enterprise are as follows:

- Adjusting profits through choosing accounting policies and methods

During the 1970s and early 1980s, a large number of studies showed that managers can exercise decision-making through the choice of accounting policy or method. Watts and Zimmerman (1978) noted that managers will choose accounting policies that reduce tax payments, reduce production costs and increase accounting profits. They have developed a positive accounting theory that shows that managers will always choose accounting policies to maximize their personal assets. Hagerman and Zmijewski (1979) find that the existence of a bonus policy that encourages managers will influence the decision to choose accounting methods. Skinner (1993) studied the relationship between the choice of accounting procedures and the establishment of investment opportunities and found that firms with compensation plans were more likely to choose to adjust profits. .

- Adjust profits through real transactions

In addition to changing accounting policies, managers can also adjust profits up or down through actual transactions. For example, a manager can accelerate sales through increases in price discounts or credit terms. In addition, managers can increase production to spread fixed costs across a larger number of product units, thereby reducing fixed costs per unit of product. By lowering the cost of goods sold, they can report a higher operating profit margin. Schipper (1989) was one of the first to suggest that earnings adjustments can be made through real-world transactions. Roychowdhury (2006) documented the types of transactions used by regulators to avoid annual reporting of losses and negative changes in profits but researchers argue that it is difficult to detect earnings adjustments. through actual actions, because there are no benchmarks to accurately define the actions that managers have taken.

- Adjust profit through cumulative total

Profits have two components, operating cash flow and cumulative total. Accruals are the manager's assessments and estimates of the cash flow from operating operations to make accounting returns a better reflection of the company's performance. Total accruals can be broken down into two components: adjustable accruals and unadjusted accruals. Unadjustable accruals are accounting adjustments to a company's operating cash flows that are imposed by the agency that issues accounting standards. Adjustable accumulation is the cash flow from operating activities recognized by managers through the flexibility of accounting rules. Because of this flexibility, adjustable accruals are the key ingredient that gives managers the opportunity to adjust profits (Dechow, 1994).

Healy (1985) first introduced the accruals used to detect earnings adjustments. Since both components of accrual are unobservable, the author assumes that the adjustable accruals in a given year are the sum of accruals in the deviation ratio of total assets and therefore, unadjusted accruals have an expected value of zero. DeAngelo (1986) argues that unadjusted accruals are subject to random and researcher's approach to detection Earnings adjustments are abnormalities in the determination of adjustable accruals that must be reflected from the change in the total accruals from year t-1 to year t. Both Healy and DeAngelo's approaches hold that

unadjustable accruals are constant and that earnings management is represented by the sum of accruals. Although Healy (1985) and DeAngelo (1986) mention profit-increasing or profit-decreasing adjustment techniques that managers can apply, the authors neglect to alter the unadjustable accruals and classifying all accruals as modifiable. Therefore, both profit-adjusted detection methods have disadvantages. To overcome this limitation, Jones (1991) introduced a linear regression approach to control the uncorrected factor of accruals. Jones estimated that adjustable accruals represent the adjustment variable for returns, since the residual from the regression of the sum of accruals is the adjustable accrual. Dechow et al. (1995) show that although all the models used to divide the sum of accruals into the adjustable accruals cannot be adjusted, the empirical analysis gives no with low level of explanation.

- Adjust profits through specific accruals

Unlike accruals, adjusting earnings over specific accruals is focusing on a single accrual of great value and requires a significant adjustment. The use of specific accruals to adjust returns is often associated with a specific industry situation, or industry-specific standard of accounting.

Marquardt and Wiedman (2004) study accruals that are used in specific situations (offers to sell shares, to buy back management rights). Among the accruals investigated were also tax costs (Dhaliwal et al., 2004) and restructuring costs (Moehrl, 2002). A specific industry can provide insight into variables for greater control over the identification of adjustable accruals. Beaver and Engel (1996) provide evidence that managers make adjustments to profits through the use of subsidy losses from loans. Finally, Beneish (1997) found that earnings management can be reflected from various indices such as the receivable index, the depreciation index, and the cost of goods sold. The author has built a profit adjustment equation based on the score indicators to evaluate the level of earnings management.

- Adjusting profits through the profit distribution method

The profit distribution method in the detection of earnings management is relatively new in research. Burgstahler and Dichev (1997) studied the density of profit distribution after adjustment. The hypothesis is that managers often have greater incentives to achieve profitability benchmarks. Disruption of profit distribution is evidence of an adjustment of profits (Burgstahler and Dichev, 1997; DeGeorge et al., 1999). McNichols (2000) points out that the mode of profit distribution allows the researcher to make strong predictions from the degree of performance adjustment of returns rather than measuring adjustable accruals. Furthermore, the profit distribution method also provides a powerful tool in detecting earnings adjustments when the number of firms adjusting for profits is large. Burgstahler and Dichev (1997) used this method and estimated that 8–12% of profitable firms made adjustments to achieve increased profits and 30–44% of firms with losses adjusted to achieve return as desired.

- Adjusting profits through profit softening method

Profit softening is designed to avoid abnormal ups and downs in profits, in other words to beautify profits, or to reduce profits during high-profit years in order to reserve profits for poor years. Imhoff (1977) found that identifying earnings management with this approach will be very difficult in distinguishing between naturally softened profits or trying to soften profits. Dechow and Skinner (2000) argue that the main purpose of GAAP is to use accruals to reduce volatility in cash flows from the underlying business of a business entity for the purpose of providing information. better in terms of the company's economic efficiency to attract capital from investors. Therefore, it becomes extremely difficult to determine the reasonable recognition of profit required by GAAP with intentionally softening profits due to the manager's opportunistic behavior. Profit softening is a form of profit adjustment and this method is rarely applied by managers.

3.4. Some models of profit adjustment

To measure the earnings management of the administrator can use many different methods. Researchers have previously introduced the earnings management measurement model by checking and comparing financial statements with the relevant bookkeeping documents of firms with suspicion of earnings management. In his thesis, the graduate student will focus on measuring methods of adjusting the profitability of enterprises through accruals.

Income statements are prepared on an accrual basis while cash flow statements are prepared on a cash basis. Therefore, the difference between the operating result on the income statement and the cash flow from operating in the cash flow statement is the non-cash accounting profit presented in the cash flow statement. Business Report. This deviation is called the cumulative value. Many studies have shown that, managers use the trick to adjust profits mainly to find ways to influence accruals on financial statements. Cash flow from operating activities on the cash flow statement is prepared on a cash basis, so it cannot be adjusted. Therefore, in order to adjust profits, managers must measure accruals and adjust the amounts. this.

Collins and Hribar (2000) used the cash flow approach from operating operations to measure the sum of accruals (TA) as follows:

Total accrual (TA_{it}) = Profit after tax before changes in capital

(NI_{it}) - Net cash flows from operating operations (OCF_{it})

Inside:

TA_{it} = Total accrual for company I in year t

NI_{it} = Profit after tax before changes in working capital of company i in year t

OCF_{it} = Net cash flow from operating activities of the company i in year t

According to the researchers, Total Accruals TA (Total Accruals) consists of two parts: The Non Discretionary Accruals (NDA) are accruals that are implemented in accordance with accounting principles, and These are called unadjustable accrues and DA (Discretionary Accruals) accruals are accruals that are influenced by managers to change the profitability of a business.

Total accumulation (TA_{it}) = Uncorrectable accumulation (NDA_{it}) + Adjustable accumulation (DA_{it})

The unadjusted cumulative portion of the NDA are the accrual values that appear or be eliminated spontaneously depending on the company's conditions, growth, business cycle length or during compliance. adhere to accounting principles of accounting. Since DA adjustable accrual is not directly observable, so in order to identify whether or not to adjust managers' returns, researchers seek to identify unadjusted accruals. NDA, from which the accrual can be adjusted DA is representative of the firm's profit adjustment. The NDA unadjustable accrual method is presented in the theoretical research models for earnings management.

4. Research results

The accounting scholars have identified that there is a potential risk in the loss of shareholder assets when there is a conflict of interest between shareholders and managers. When managers are explicitly or explicitly rewarded based on the company's performance, they may conceal the actual performance by adjusting profits for a higher bonus. . This earnings management also increases asymmetric information between managers and investors. Investors often rate stocks and make buying and selling decisions based on information collected on financial reports. Therefore, providing false information can cause investors to make wrong decisions. Several studies have shown that investors are very sensitive to earnings management. Dechow et al. (1996) provide evidence that there is a 9% decline in the stock price of firms under investigation by the SEC for earnings management. Vo Van Nhi and Hoang Cam Trang (2013) examine the relationship between earnings

management and bankruptcy risk of 85 companies listed on the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange (HOSE) for the accounting year. 2011. The study used model of Leuz et al (2003) to determine earnings management and used Altman's Z-Index (2000) to determine the risk of bankruptcy. As such, the regulatory behavior can be detrimental to the investor and even affect the real performance of the company. The results show that the adjusted profitability level is similar to the risk of bankruptcy: Companies located in safe areas, not at risk of bankruptcy have the lowest average earnings management level; Firms that are in warning zones, which may be at risk of bankruptcy, have higher average earnings management; Companies located in dangerous, high-risk areas of bankruptcy have the highest average earnings management.

Profit adjustment is discovered in both domestic and foreign firms. Profit accounting information is important information that state regulators, banks, and credit institutions, and investors use to evaluate the financial situation of a business. Adjusting profits will reduce the quality and reliability of the company's financial statements. Not to mention, when competitors adjust profits too much, other businesses also find it difficult to maintain good behaviors, eventually leading to abnormal competition on earnings management, accounting information lost in comparison. In comparison, users will find it difficult to differentiate the differences between each enterprise. In addition, profit adjustment is only aimed at achieving the optimal level of immediate profit in the short term, without attaching to the improvement of product reform, the organization of operations of the business, thus adjusting profitability. may bring risks to the growth of the business in the future.

Table 1: Statistical table describing variables in the earnings management measurement model

Factors	n	mean	Standard deviation	Min	max
TA_t/A_{t-1}	1056	0.0559789	0.1419892	-1.058519	2.521187
$1/A_{t-1}$	1056	0.3071175	0.4759809	0.0004677	5.428894
$(DtREV_t - DtREC_t)/A_{t-1}$	1056	0.1434569	0.4413821	-3.784412	3.457437
PPE_t/A_{t-1}	1056	0.222839	0.2195149	0.000064	2.746061
$DtCFO_t/A_{t-1}$	1056	0.0001325	0.1721139	-2.196031	1.131845

Table 2: Results of regression of the general least squares GLS model

factors	P-value
$1/A_{t-1}$	0.00892****
	[3.07]
$(DtREV_t - DtREC_t)/A_{t-1}$	0.0667***
	[21.12]
PPE_t/A_{t-1}	0.0885****
	[24.88]
$DtCFO_t/A_{t-1}$	-0.513****
	[-72.92]
Sig.: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$	

With the results of testing the hypotheses, we find that the impact level of 4 independent variables on the dependent variable is statistically significant. The model selected in phase 1 is the GLS model because the cointegration and covariance changes can be overcome. Finally we have a model for summing non-adjustable accruals (NDA t) as follows:

$$\text{NDA } t = 0.00892 * 1 / \text{At-1} + 0.0667 * (\text{DtREVt-DtREct}) / \text{At-1} + 0.0885 * \text{PPEt} / \text{At-1} \\ - 0.513 * \text{DtCFOt} / \text{At-1}$$

5. Conclusion

From the results of experimental analysis, it is found that in 16 hypotheses are given: In case of separating negative and positive DA data: With negative DA data, the study shows that there are 4 hypotheses with the correct results as expected. The PhD student's are: Effects of Ownership Concentration, manager's ownership ratio, foreign investor's ownership ratio and financial leverage on corporate profits; With positive DA data, the empirical results show that there are 3 accepted research theories: The impact of state ownership ratio, foreign ownership ratio and independent audit on profit adjustment. In the case of aggregating negative and positive DA data, the study proves that there are 6 accepted research theories: Impact of the concentration of ownership, the rate of state ownership, the rate of foreign ownership, business size, financial leverage and independent audit to adjust profits. The remaining hypotheses have results contrary to the expectations of the graduate students. Thus, the empirical results on the impact of the attributes of public administration on the adjustment of corporate profits when in the case of aggregation of negative and positive DA data, separate results of each type of project are ignored. therefore, the overall results are different from the negative and positive DA data separation. In addition, the study also shows that the relationships that exist between factors of corporate governance and the adjustment of corporate profits are largely inversely affected, which shows management practices. Good companies will contribute to limiting earnings management in corporate businesses

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